

Solvent effect on coumarin dye : Calculation of ground and excited state dipole moments

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Abstract : Absorption and fluorescence spectra of 7-diethylamino-4-methyl coumarin in polar and non-polar solvents have been studied. The excited state dipole moment (μ_e) has been found to be more than the ground state dipole moment (μ_g). These values have been compared with the computed value by using *ab initio* method at 6-31G* level and are in good agreement with the experimental result.

Keywords : 7-Diethylamino-4-methyl coumarin, polar and non-polar solvents, *ab initio* method, dipole moments, absorption spectra.

Introduction

Coumarins and their derivatives occur widely in nature. Many natural and synthetic coumarin derivatives are in use to exploit their biological, chemical and physical properties. Coumarins are useful probes in different chemical and photochemical studies¹⁻⁴. Many of them are highly fluorescent and have potential application as fluorescent indicators⁵, sunburn preventives⁶, estimation of enzymes⁷ etc.

The knowledge of absorption and fluorescence characteristics of these compounds with different substituent under varying conditions of solvents, temperature^{8,9}, pH^{10,11} is important in understanding the working of tunable dye lasers and operating them at maximum efficiency. In recent years, due to the fast progress in photochemistry, studies of electric dipole moment in the excited state have gained great importance. The excitation of a molecule by a photon causes redistribution of the electron density and correspondingly a change in the dipole moment. A non-equilibrium state is created as the solvent environment can not follow the sudden change in the dipole moment. During the relaxation of the solvent towards a new equilibrium state, the interaction energy between the solvent and solute changes and hence the fluorescence spectra of the probe molecule shifts¹². This result in an increase or decrease of the excited state dipole moments compared to that in the ground state. Among the numerous ways of

determining excited state dipole moment (μ_e), the solvent shift method is the simplest and the most widely used. The observation of solvent induced shift of electronic bands of molecule has been used extensively in order to study the changes in electronic distribution in excited states of solute molecules¹³.

The solvent shifts can be accounted in terms of the overall effect of the interaction forces (which are mainly of van der Waal's type) on the π electron system of the molecule. It is also known that as the π electron system become less localized, the transition energy becomes smaller resulting in a bathochromic shift (red shift) and its opposite effect gives rise to a hypsochromic shift (blue shift). In order to assign the electronic transition as $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ or $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$, the solvent shift method is very informative. It is known that as the polarity of solvents increase $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ bands show a red shift while $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ bands show a blue shift. The solvatochromic shifts were also used for the determination of the excited state dipole moments of some coumarins¹⁴⁻²¹. The coumarin molecule as such in aqueous solution is non-fluorescent, but they do become highly fluorescent on substitution^{22,23}. The emission characteristic of a fluorophor depends upon the position as well as the nature of the surrounding medium^{24,25}.

Most of the methods available for the determination of the singlet-excited state are based on the spectral shift caused externally by electrochromism²⁶. In both these

techniques Lippert-Mataga equation^{26,27} is used, which is based on the spectral shift of absorption and fluorescence maximum and solvent polarity parameters, dielectric constant (ϵ) and refractive index (n). The solvatochromic method to determine the excited state dipole moments is preferred due to simplicity of the experimental procedure and ease of data analysis.

Theory :

The bulk dielectric constant (ϵ) and refractive index (n) of a solvent strongly effect²⁸⁻³⁰ the dipole moments of the solute molecules. An interaction with the environment affects the various electronic states in a different way. The interaction between the solvent and solute molecule depends upon dielectric constant (ϵ) and refractive index (n) of the solvent and the dipole moment of the solute molecules. By applying quantum-mechanical second order perturbation theory³¹, following equations have been obtained for the absorption (ν_a) and emission (ν_f) band shifts (in the wave numbers) in different solvents of varying permittivity (ϵ) and the refractive index (n) :

$$\nu_a - \nu_f = m_1 f(\epsilon, n) + \text{const} \quad (1)$$

$$\nu_a + \nu_f = -m_2 [f(\epsilon, n) + 2g(n)] + \text{const} \quad (2)$$

with

$$f(\epsilon, n) = \frac{2n^2 + 1}{n^2 + 2} \left[\frac{\epsilon - 1}{\epsilon - 2} - \frac{n^2 - 1}{n^2 + 2} \right] \quad (3)$$

Being the solvent polarity function and

$$g(n) = \frac{3}{2} \left[\frac{n^4 - 1}{(n + 2)^2} \right] \quad (4)$$

with

$$m_1 = \frac{2(\mu_e - \mu_g)^2}{hca^3} \quad (5)$$

and

$$m_2 = \frac{2(\mu_e^2 - \mu_g^2)}{hca^3} \quad (6)$$

The parameters m_1 and m_2 occurring in eqs. (1) and (2) for the differences ($\nu_a - \nu_f$) and sum ($\nu_a + \nu_f$) of the wave numbers which are linear functions of the solvent polarity parameters $f(\epsilon, n)$ and $f(\epsilon, n) + 2g(n)$ can be determined from the slopes of the straight lines. In eqs. (5) and (6), μ_e and μ_g represent the dipole moments in the excited and ground state respectively, h being Planck's

constant, c the velocity of light in vacuum and ' a ' is Onsager's cavity radius of the solute molecule. If the ground and excited states are parallel, based on the eqs. (5) and (6), the following equations are obtained.

$$\mu_g = \frac{m_2 - m_1}{2} \sqrt{\frac{hca^3}{2m_1}} \quad (7)$$

$$\mu_e = \frac{m_2 + m_1}{2} \sqrt{\frac{hca^3}{2m_1}} \quad (8)$$

The validity of eqs. (7) and (8) is based on the certain assumption like considering both the dipole moments collinear and has same ' a ' value in both the ground and excited states. The Onsager cavity radius ' a ' has been taken as half the distance between two extreme high charge centres because they probably provide the strongest dipole vector component in the molecule studied here.

Experimental

7-Diethylamino-4-methyl coumarin was obtained from Sigma Aldrich Chemicals (USA) and was used as received without further purification. The molecular structure of the dye is shown in Fig. 1. All the solvents used in the present work, were of spectroscopic grade and are

Fig. 1. Optimized structures of 7-diethylamino-4-methyl coumarin.

found to be transparent and non-fluorescent in the range of excitation and fluorescence emission. The absorption and fluorescence spectra were recorded using Shimadzu UV-Vis spectrophotometer (UV 2450). The fluorescence spectra were recorded using Shimadzu RF5301 PC fluorescence spectrophotometer. The uncertainty in the measured wavelength of absorption and emission maxima is ± 0.1 nm and ± 0.5 nm respectively. All the measurements were carried out at room temperature keeping dye concentration 10^{-4} M to 10^{-6} M in order to avoid self-absorption.

Computational method :

The geometry of the dye has been optimised using *ab initio* quantum chemical method at 6-31G* level. The accuracy of the energy criteria is maintained at r.m.s. gradient 0.1 kcal/Å mol. The Polak-Reiberra algorithm is used for fast and accurate computation. The Onsager radii a' has also been calculated theoretically and is mentioned at the appropriate place. The Hyperchem 7.52 package program has been employed for this purpose³².

Results and discussion

The effect of solvents on the absorption and emission spectra of 7-diethylamino-4-methyl coumarin is shown in Figs. 2–10. The observed absorption and emission spec-

Fig. 2. Emission spectrum of coumarin dye in DMSO.

Fig. 3. Emission spectrum of coumarin dye in DMF.

Fig. 4. Emission spectrum of coumarin dye in ethanol.

Fig. 5. Emission spectrum of coumarin dye in acetone.

Fig. 6. Emission spectrum of coumarin dye in ethyl acetate.

Fig. 7. Emission spectrum of coumarin dye in toluene.

Fig. 8. Emission spectrum of coumarin dye in 1,4-dioxane.

Fig. 9. Emission spectrum of coumarin dye in cyclohexane.

Fig. 10. Emission spectrum of coumarin dye in CCl₄.

tra of the dye is broad with shift depending on the solvent used (DMSO-CCl₄). The charge transfer band shows a shift of about 0–15 nm in the absorption spectra on changing the solvent from DMSO to CCl₄.

A large spectral shift is observed in the emission spectra (0–53 nm) as compared to the absorption spectra. The less pronounced shift in the absorption spectra observed in all the solvents studied implies that the ground state energy distribution is not affected to a greater extent possibly due to less polar nature of the dye in the ground state than in the excited state. This pronounced shift in

the emission spectra clearly indicated the dipole moment of the excited state is higher compared to that in the ground state. In such cases, the relaxed excited state (S₁) will be energetically stabilised relative to the ground state (S₀) and a significant red-shift of the fluorescence will be observed. The wave numbers of absorption and fluorescence emission maxima along with solvent parameters refractive index (*n*) and dielectric constant (ϵ) are summarized in Table 1 for the dye under probe. In order to estimate the ground state and excited state dipole moments of the solute molecule, the solvent polarity $f(\epsilon, n)$ and $f(\epsilon, n) + 2g(n)$ parameters were calculated and are tabulated in Table 2.

Table 1. Physical constants of solvent and spectral data of 7-diethylamino-4-methyl coumarin

Sl. no.	Solvent	ν_a (cm ⁻¹)	ν_f (cm ⁻¹)	ϵ	<i>n</i>
1.	DMSO	26737	22779	47.24	1.479
2.	DMF	26954	23148	38.25	1.430
3.	Ethanol	26809	22370	24.30	1.361
4.	Acetone	27322	23529	21.01	1.359
5.	Ethyl acetate	27855	23752	6.08	1.372
6.	Toluene	27855	24630	2.38	1.497
7.	CCl ₄	21027	24509	2.24	1.459
8.	1,4-Dioxane	27548	24213	2.22	1.422
9.	Cyclohexane	27247	25380	2.02	1.426

Table 2. Calculated values for solvent polarity parameter $f(\epsilon, n)$, $g(n)$ and $f(\epsilon, n) + 2g(n)$

Sl. no.	Solvent	$\nu_a - \nu_f$ (cm ⁻¹)	$\nu_a + \nu_f$ (cm ⁻¹)	$f(\epsilon, n)$	$g(n)$	$f(\epsilon, n) + 2g(n)$
1.	DMSO	3958	49516	0.841	0.648	1.489
2.	DMF	3806	50102	0.839	0.583	1.423
3.	Ethanol	4438	49180	0.812	0.491	1.303
4.	Acetone	3793	50851	0.792	0.489	1.281
5.	Ethyl acetate	4103	51607	0.493	0.506	0.999
6.	Toluene	3225	52485	0.029	0.671	0.700
7.	CCl ₄	2518	51536	0.099	0.448	0.995
8.	1,4-Dioxane	3335	51761	0.044	0.573	0.617
9.	Cyclohexane	1867	52627	-0.003	0.578	0.575

The respective spectral shifts ($\nu_a - \nu_f$) and ($\nu_a + \nu_f$) for the solute molecules which are observed in various solvents, are plotted as a polarity function $f(\epsilon, n)$ and $f(\epsilon, n) + 2g(n)$ respectively are given in Figs. 11 and 12. A linear regression was done and the data was fit to a straight

Fig. 11. Plot of $(v_a - v_f)$ vs of $f(\epsilon, n)$ of 7-diethylamino-4-methyl coumarin in solvents listed in Table 1.

Fig. 12. Plot of $(v_a - v_f)$ vs of $f(\epsilon, n) + 2g(n)$ of 7-diethylamino-4-methyl coumarin in solvents listed in Table 1.

line for both the plots whose slopes are taken as m_1 and m_2 . For polar solute like 7-diethylamino-4-methyl coumarin, the interaction with non-polar solvents depends on the dipole-induced-dipole forces, while with aprotic (polar but non-hydrogen bonding) solvents, the solute-solvent interaction depends on dipole-dipole forces. In protic solvents like alcohol, in addition to dipole interaction, specific interaction such as hydrogen bonding may be effective as the intermolecular charge transfer (ICT) character is favourable for hydrogen bonding with hydroxy

group in alcohols. With the increasing solvent polarity, both absorption and emission band undergo a bathochromic shift, the latter being more pronounced than the former.

The Onsager's cavity radius is calculated by taking the distance between the two extreme charge centres in the solute molecule. The ground and excited state dipole moments calculated using eqs. (7) and (8) are summarised in Table 3 along with slopes m_1 and m_2 . The ground and excited state dipole moments are also been calculated by using quantum chemical *ab initio* method at 6-31G* level

Table 3. Dipole moments, slopes (m_1 and m_2) and radius of 7-diethylamino-4-methyl coumarin

Solute	m_2 (cm^{-1})	Radius (Å)	μ_g (D)	μ_e (D)	$\Delta\mu$ (D)
7DEA4MC	1527	3.45	12.76	16.01	3.25
	3174	(3.62)	(13.10)	(16.95)	(3.85)

The numbers in parentheses are computed values at 6-31G* level.

and are given in Table 3. The calculated values of ground and excited state dipole moments from the eqs. (7) and (8) and by 6-31G* level correlate well.

Conclusion :

In summary, we have described the solvent effect by examining dipole moments of the coumarin laser dye (7-diethylamino-4-methyl coumarin) in nine solvents. A bathochromic shift is observed while increasing the polarity of the solvent indicating $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition which is further confirmed by calculating the dipole moments using eqs. (7) and (8). We found that the solute molecule possess a higher dipole moment in the excited state than in the ground state in all the nine solvent systems. This clearly indicates that the excited state of 7-diethylamino-4-ethyl coumarin is more polar than the ground state.

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